

The Intersection between AI Literacy and Media and Information Literacy Scales - A Bibliometric Study and Conceptual Analysis

Annex 2:

Figures (4,6,7)

Figure 4. A network analysis of keyword co-occurrence in WoS literature on media, information, and AI literacies (N=8,624)

Source: Own elaboration

